

Effect Of Social Responsibility Through Youth Organization On Community Empowerment

Tri Joko Raharjo, Joko Sutarto, Harianingsih, Didik Wiyono, Mohammad Miftah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 05, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: October 06, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Empowerment, Social Responsibility, Youth Organization</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13895911</p>	<p><i>This study aims to describe the forms of activities in social responsibility and youth participation in youth empowerment. This research uses a qualitative approach with the grounded theory method. Setting research on youth activities in the South Sri Rejeki village, Kalibanteng Kidul. Data collection using observation, documentation and interview. Data analysis technique used is interactive analysis. Triangulation is done to explain the validity of the data with various sources in finding the information needed. The results of this study indicate that youth empowerment includes a) the reasons for youth involvement namely hobbies in common, caring for the community, self-awareness, stepping stones to education, readiness work, and as a form of worship b) youth empowerment seen from the planning, implementation, evaluation to development c) factors supporting youth involvement, self-awareness and support from the management and community leaders. While the inhibiting factor, the difference in youth leisure time d) the impact of youth empowerment is seen from personal skills, academic skills, skills vocational and social skills. So it can be concluded that in addition to youth programs from government, child-friendly village program can be one of the efforts to increase empowerment young man.</i></p>

Introduction

Youth as a pillar of the nation has the potential to continue to be developed in order to contribute to community empowerment[1]. Youth organizations have a social responsibility to bring change to improve the welfare of the surrounding communities. In accordance with the regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 / HUK / 2010 regarding the basic guidelines of youth organizations stating that youth organizations are social organizations that are used and as a means of community development facilities that are the social responsibility of young people to the community in the village area[2]. The target of the establishment of youth clubs is to be realized and social responsibility in the implementation of development so as to realize prosperity that can be enjoyed by the entire community[3]. The potential possessed by the youth group is expected to be able to overcome various kinds of problems faced by the community both preventive, rehabilitative as well as the development of their environmental potential[4]. Productive youth according to experts are young people who have innovation and creativity, enthusiasm to try, commitment to work[1]. The function of youth clubs is effective if the youths who become members can run a social welfare business, organize education and training for the community, organize community empowerment, especially young people in the surrounding environment in an integrated, directed and sustainable manner[5]. Youth clubs will be effective if they are organizers of entrepreneurial spirit development activities for young people in the community[6]. Youth organizations have a social responsibility to foster and develop a spirit of togetherness, a spirit of family life, social solidarity[7]. Youth must be able to strengthen the values of wisdom in the framework of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia. The moral obligation of youth organizations is to foster the creativity of young people, to create a recreational, educative, economically productive environment, and other social activities by utilizing the potential of social welfare in their environment independently[6]. Youth organization provides assistance and assistance for social advocacy, communication network systems, cooperation, information and partnerships[3]. From the background that has been described, the purpose of this study is to find out the factors that influence youth in their social responsibility towards community empowerment[8]. The research framework shows in figure 1.

Fig. 1 Research Framework

Method

The method used is a qualitative and quantitative approach. with a case study on Sri Rejeki's t reefs. The population was 100 young people and the sample was 50 people. The research design is in the form of descriptive qualitative and interpretation of phenomena in the community. At the beginning of the study observations and analysis of problems in the Sri Rejeki youth group. The next step is data retrieval. Analysis of the validity and reliability of the data taken is done quantitatively. The instrument used was a questionnaire with a Likert scale. Research variables include the independence variable which includes self control and respect, effort and participation, self direction and helping others. The dependent variable is youth organization. Sample and Data Collection

Results and Discussion

A. Self Control

Youth organization is a social organization based on youth and was founded on the basis of the youth's concern for problems and the desire to empower the community[9]. The youth are expected to be the next generation and make changes in a sustainable manner. Youth organizations have a social responsibility to the surrounding environment[10]. From the results of the self control variable questionnaire, there are several indicators such as being unselfish, prioritizing others without expecting reward (altruism), having empathy, willingness to fight[11]. The validity and reliability of the self control variable can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Reliability and Validity of Self Control

Variable	SLF ≥ 0.30	t-value	Error	Reliability		Validity
				CR ≥ 0.70	VE ≥ 0.50	
<i>Self control</i>				0.78	0.51	(Good Reliability)
Being unselfish	0.42	5.50	0.83			Good
Altruism	0.53	3.67	0.54			Good
Williangness to fight	0.56	7.75	0.68			Good

In table 1 that the variable self control has good reliability and good validity. The loading factor value of the indicator variables include being unselfish, altruism, willingness to fight in a row of 0.42; 0.530.56. The t-value for each indicator variable being unselfish, altruism, willingness to fight in a row of 5.50; 3.67; 7.75. This is in accordance with the provisions of an indicator variable having good validity if the loading factor value ≥ 0.3 and t-value > 1.96 . The reliability value for CR is 0.78 and VE is 0.51. Indicators of the variables will meet the reliability requirements if the test value $CR > 0.70$ and $VE > 0.50$. The younger generation was born as a world civilization, youth movements have created independence for the State of Indonesia. But along with the development era, youth organizations consisting of young people face social problems due to modernization and globalization[12]. Youth need self control so that they can always contribute to their role as social control and agents of change. Although the youth organization in political ethics as a social creature emphasizes the dimension of responsibility for what is done, the personal conscience of each youth remains self control for the progress of his organization[13].

A. Effort and participation

Youth organization as a youth organization is a place for young people to participate as citizens in community empowerment. Social movements are carried out as organized collective actions as a conscious and planned mobilization effort for community empowerment[14]. Social movements require efforts from youth groups by emphasizing participation in the movement as a normative practice. The following table 2 presents the reliability and validity of the variable effort and participation consisting of social welfare organizers, education providers, empowerment organizers, awareness keepers and developers, social solidarity growers, increase of creativity.

Table 2. Reliability and Validity of Effort and participation

Variable	SLF ≥ 0.30	t-value	Error	Reliability		Validity
				CR ≥ 0.70	VE ≥ 0.50	
<i>Effort and Participation</i>				0.72	0.54	(Good Reliability)
Social welfare	0.54	5.43	0.67			Good
Education providers	0.46	6.21	0.59			Good
Empowerment organizers	0.38	5.24	0.78			Good
Social Solidarity	0.49	5.19	0.65			Good
Awareness keepers	0.57	6.28	0.69			Good
Increase creativity	0.53	5.42	0.72			Good

In table 2 that the variable self control has good reliability and good validity. The loading factor value of the six indicator variables include social welfare, education providers, empowerment organizers, social solidarity, awareness keepers, increase creativity in a row of 0.54; 0.46; 0.38; 0.49; 0.57; 0.53. The t-value for each indicator variable social welfare, education providers, empowerment organizers, social solidarity, awareness keepers, increase creativity in a row of 5.43; 6.21; 5.24; 5.19; 6.28; 5.42. This is in accordance with the provisions of an indicator variable having good validity if the loading factor value ≥ 0.3 and t-value ≥ 1.96 . The reliability value for CR is 0.72 and VE is 0.54. Indicators of the variables will meet the reliability requirements if the test value $CR \geq 0.70$ and $VE \geq 0.50$. Some of the roles of youth organization include inviting young people who are not yet members of youth organization to join in, instilling a disciplined attitude to each member and committing to every activity carried out by the organization, all members must be active and understand each other's job description. Youth must be able to identify the potential in the area. Youth also need to work together with village officials in carrying out their activities[2].

B. Self Direction

The main task of youth clubs is self direction, giving direction and understanding and providing solutions to problems that occur in the community[15]. Indicators on self direction variables include facilitative roles, educational roles, representational roles, technical roles. Validity and Reliability of the self direction variable are in table 3.

Table 3. Reliability and Validity of Self Direction

Variable	SLF ≥ 0.30	t-value	Error	Reliability		Validity
				CR ≥ 0.70	VE ≥ 0.50	
<i>Self direction</i>				0.81	0.58	(Good Reliability)
Facilitaties	0.57	5.60	0.68			Good
Educational	0.48	4.98	0.63			Good
Representational	0.39	5.12	0.72			Good
Technical	0.52	5.65	0.58			Good

In table 3 that the variable self direction has good reliability and good validity. The loading factor value of the six indicator variables include facilitates role, educational role, representational role, technical role in a row of 0.57; 0.48; 0.39; 0.52. The t-value for each indicator variable facilitates role, educational role, representational role, technical role in a row of 5.60; 4.98; 5.12; 5.65. This is in accordance with the provisions of an indicator variable having good validity if the loading factor value ≥ 0.3 and t-value ≥ 1.96 . The reliability value for CR is 0.81 and VE is 0.58. Indicators of the variables will meet the reliability requirements if the test value CR ≥ 0.70 and VE ≥ 0.50 . As a facilitating role, the youth group acts as an effective intermediary and successor of information from stakeholders to members or vice versa. Youth organizations form group facilitation for easy access in developing the skills of their members[16].

C. Helping Others

Youth organizations have a moral responsibility to be able to help the community. Caring grows a sense of usefulness for others. Empathy and caring behavior towards the community must be developed to prevent the emergence of anti-social. Helping other variables have indicators including self gain, personal values, norms and empathy. The following shows the reliability and validity values of the other self variables in table 4.

Table 4. Reliability and Validity of Helping Other

Variable	SLF ≥ 0.30	t-value	Error	Reliability		Validity
				CR ≥ 0.70	VE ≥ 0.50	
<i>Helping other</i>				0.77	0.51	(Good Reliability)
Self gain	0.43	5.21	0.76			Good
Personal values	0.49	5.43	0.69			Good
Norms	0.52	4.98	0.72			Good
Empathy	0.54	4.86	0.68			Good

In table 4 that the variable helping other has good reliability and good validity. The loading factor value of the six indicator variables include self again, personal values, norms, empathy in a row of 0.43; 0.49; 0.52; 0.54. The t-value for each indicator variable self again, personal values, norms, empathy in a row of 5.21; 5.43; 4.98; 4.86. This is in accordance with the provisions of an indicator variable having good validity if the loading factor value ≥ 0.3 and t-value ≥ 1.96 . The reliability value for CR is 0.77 and VE is 0.51. Indicators of the variables will meet the reliability requirements if the test value CR ≥ 0.70 and VE ≥ 0.50 . Helping other behaviors include sharing, cooperative, helping, honesty and considering the rights and obligations of others[17]. Factors that influence youth organizations have helping others include socialization where the socialization can be in the form of helping to give attention[18]. The second factor is mood and feeling because if a person's feelings are good then interacting with others and accepting other people's circumstances will be easier. Another factor is the environmental situation where the youth is located, communication and language as well as the responses given and received[11].

Conclusion

The Youth Organization as a place for youth has a social responsibility towards the community empowerment process. These social responsibilities include dimensions of self control, effort and participation, self direction and helping others. From the results of the calculation of validity and reliability it can be concluded that social responsibility influences community empowerment. The programs run by the youth organization are innovative and creative and sustainable. The output of the youth organization is community welfare.

Acknowledgment

This research was partially funded by Program Penelitian DIPA Fakultas Tahun 2020 Number : 42.11.5/UN37/PPK.5.1/2020 from Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Semarang. The authors declare no competing interests or any conflicts of financial interests.

References

- [1] D. Frain, J. Groeneweg, and J. Harder, "2019 Evaluation Report for Omaha Girls Rock—A Youth Empowerment Organization," 2019.
- [2] M. J. Puluwulawa, "Peran Karang Taruna dalam Menciptakan Pemuda Produktif Di Desa Barakati Kecamatan Batudaa Kabupaten Gorontalo," *Skripsi*, vol. 1, no. 121410110, 2012.
- [3] A. C. Alexander, C. O. Obong'o, P. Chavan, M. W. Vander Weg, and K. D. Ward, "Applying the Problem Behavior Theory to adolescent drug use among a cross-sectional sample of boys participating in a community-based youth organization," *Substance Use & Misuse*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 610-621, 2018.
- [4] B. Checkoway and K. Richards-Schuster, "Youth participation in community evaluation research," *American journal of evaluation*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 21-33, 2003.

- [5] D. M. Griffith *et al.*, "Organizational empowerment in community mobilization to address youth violence," *American journal of preventive medicine*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. S89-S99, 2008.
- [6] P. Gurey, "Rural Development through Youth Organization and Rural Library Services: Tagore's Idea on Rural Reconstruction," *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, vol. 7, pp. 179-188, 2017.
- [7] L. Q. Kolano and L. T. Davila, "Transformative learning of refugee girls within a community youth organization serving Southeast Asians in North Carolina," *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 119-133, 2019.
- [8] N. R. Leonard *et al.*, "'Coming from the place of walking with the youth—That feeds everything': A mixed methods case study of a runaway and homeless youth organization," *Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 443-459, 2017.
- [9] J. K. London, K. Zimmerman, and N. Erbstein, "Youth-Led research and evaluation: Tools for youth, organizational, and community development," *New Directions for Evaluation*, vol. 2003, no. 98, pp. 33-45, 2003.
- [10] I. Mudofir, M. F. Maftuh, and T. Rahayu, "Pelatihan Strategi Revitalisasi Karang Taruna Desa Doho, Kecamatan Dolopo, Kabupaten Madiun," *DIKEMAS (Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat)*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2019.
- [11] A. R. Smith, B. L. Garton, and T. J. Kitchel, "Beyond mere enrollment: Level of youth organization participation as a predictor of collegiate academic success and retention," *Journal of Agricultural Education*, vol. 51, no. 2, p. 24, 2010.
- [12] E. Odera, M. Brennan, M. Cahill, and J. Malcolm, "Innovation for Agricultural Training and Education Youth Extremism Series, Paper 5: Fostering Empathy in Youth through Participatory Research and Evaluation."
- [13] C. Patler and R. G. Gonzales, "Framing citizenship: Media coverage of anti-deportation cases led by undocumented immigrant youth organisations," *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, vol. 41, no. 9, pp. 1453-1474, 2015.
- [14] N. Popova, "Youth Leaders in the Organization of Work with Young People at Industrial Enterprises," *CITISE*, vol. 1, p. 18, 2018.
- [15] E.-K. Prokkola and J. Ridanpää, "Youth organizations, citizenship, and guidelines for tourism in the wake of mass tourism in Finland," *Citizenship studies*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 359-377, 2017.
- [16] A. Mcadams-Mahmoud, "A Mixed Methods Study of Perspective-Taking, Empathy, and Trust in Police and Youth," 2019.
- [17] S.-M. Vierimaa, "Transnational Political Activities of the Swedish Finn Youth Organization," *Nordic Journal of Migration Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 12-19, 2017.
- [18] L. B. Wadu, I. Ladamay, and S. R. Jama, "Keterlibatan Warga Negara Dalam Pembangunan Berkelanjutan Melalui Kegiatan Karang Taruna," *Jurnal Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1-8, 2019.

Author Information

Tri Joko Raharjo

Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia

Joko Sutarto

Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia,

Harianingsih

Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia,

Didik Wiyono

Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia,

Mohammad Miftah

Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia,